

A Randomized Comparative Study of Blood Flow Restriction Therapy and Cyriax Technique on Strength and Quality of Life in Lateral Epicondylitis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Lateral epicondylitis is a musculoskeletal condition caused by inflammation of the tendons of the Extensor carpi radialis longus and Extensor carpi radialis brevis, resulting in local pain, tenderness, wrist and hand muscle weakness, and functional disability. Cyriax is a manual therapeutic approach while Blood flow restriction therapy is an advanced exercise therapeutic approach. Blood flow restriction treatment is a novel training strategy used in athletic activities and therapeutic contexts to increase muscular strength and enlargement. Although Cyriax and blood flow restriction therapy are beneficial therapeutic approaches for Lateral epicondylitis, there is no evidence to suggest which is more efficient. **Purpose:** To compare the effects of Blood Flow Restriction therapy and the Cyriax technique, as adjuncts to eccentric exercises, on muscle strength and quality of life in individuals with lateral epicondylitis. **Methods:** Thirty participants (n = 30) diagnosed with lateral epicondylitis were randomly allocated into two groups: a Blood Flow Restriction therapy group and a Cyriax technique group. Both groups received nine treatment sessions (three sessions per week for three weeks) along with eccentric exercises. Outcome measures included muscle strength (assessed using a handheld dynamometer and pinch gauge) and quality of life (assessed using the Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation questionnaire) recorded before and after the intervention. **Results:** Although both groups showed significant effects in pre-to-post-test comparison ($p < 0.05$), the between-group analysis failed to show any significant difference statistically (> 0.05) in all the outcome measures. Thus, it can be inferred that both therapies are equally effective in Lateral epicondylitis thereby accepting the null hypothesis. **Conclusion:** Blood Flow Restriction therapy and the Cyriax technique, when combined with eccentric exercises, are equally effective in improving muscle strength and quality of life in individuals with lateral epicondylitis.

Keywords: Lateral Epicondylitis, Blood Flow Restriction Therapy, Cyriax Technique, Muscle Strength, Quality of Life, Eccentric Exercises

INTRODUCTION

Lateral Epicondylitis is the most prevalent diagnosis for those with elbow injuries. This ailment causes discomfort and tenderness on the lateral side of the humerus and painful restricted dorsiflexion of the wrist, middle finger, or both. Although Lateral epicondylitis can occur at any age, the peak prevalence is between the ages of 30 and 60.[1] It is more commonly associated with sports activities in younger people and occupational activities in elderly patients. Although tennis elbow only accounts for 5-10% of all occurrences of lateral epicondylitis, 40-

50% of tennis players encounter the ailment at some point in their lives. It is caused by tendinopathy in the forearm's extensor muscles. These muscles emerge from the lateral epicondylar region of the distal humerus. The insertion of the extensor carpi radialis brevis is implicated in several situations.[2] Epicondylitis is caused mostly by contractile overloads that continuously stress the tendon around the humeral attachment. It frequently arises during repetitive upper extremity tasks such as computer usage, hard lifting, forearm pronation and supination, and continuous stimulation. Resisted supine position or wrist flexion, especially with a fully extended arm,

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is widely employed to simulate symptoms. The pain is frequently felt directly beneath the Lateral epicondyle, across the extensor tendon bulk.[3] Multidisciplinary therapy is effective in treating tendinopathy. The treatment plan includes NSAIDs, corticosteroid injection, acupuncture, autologous blood injection, tissue stress management, manual therapies, and strapping. Tennis elbow care should be centered on exercises, which are presently the finest management alternative available to us. [4] Eccentric exercises are beneficial for treating Lateral Epicondylitis. Eccentric workouts contend that eccentric exercise increases tendon strain, as a result, the tendon experiences structural modification, often known as hypertrophic alterations. These workouts take advantage of the muscular elongation period to boost muscle development and strength. Current research suggests that the therapeutic exercise regimen for painful tendinopathy should include eccentric activities that target the afflicted area. [5] Blood flow restriction training is a sort of strengthening exercise in which a tourniquet or a pressurized cuff is applied to the proximal area of the body part being trained. Following that, the tourniquet's cuff is inflated to a specified pressure, resulting in partial arterial and full venous occlusion. Blood flow restriction training replicates the effects of high-intensity exercise by simulating a hypoxic environment with pressurized cuffs. Muscle and tendon injuries are known to recover faster in hypoxic conditions.[6] People suffering from lateral epicondylitis have significant loss of muscle strength and handgrip function, which must be addressed while simultaneously making strengthening exercises more challenging. As a result, when high-intensity exercise might generate a hypoxic environment, Blood flow restriction training can be useful, but only with low-intensity exercise, which is more readily tolerated in those with pain or other inflammatory disorders, such as lateral epicondylitis. [7] There is an abundance of evidence that supports the use of Cyriax in the treatment of lateral epicondylitis. Cyriax used deep transverse friction therapy in combination with mill manipulation to treat lateral epicondylitis. Deep transverse friction, also known as deep abrasion therapy, is a form of connective tissue massage that targets soft tissue components like tendons. It was created experimentally by Cyriax and is now widely utilized in therapeutic therapy. [8] Cyriax suggests

that manipulation be conducted immediately after the Deep transverse friction if the patient has a full range of passive elbow extension. If passive elbow extension is restricted, the manipulative force will be directed toward the elbow joint rather than the common extensor tendon, potentially resulting in traumatic arthritis. It's characterized as a passive movement at the end of the range in which all slack is gathered and a low-amplitude, high-velocity push is produced. Tennis elbow participants can decrease pain, enhance grip strength, and boost functional output by combining low-load exercises with cyriax physiotherapy. [9] As there is supporting evidence that suggests both cyriax and blood flow restriction training showed superior and useful effects individually, However, the comparative benefits of eccentric exercises with blood flow restriction and cyriax physiotherapy to alleviate lateral epicondylitis have not been researched to the best of our ability. Hence this study aimed to assess the effects of blood flow restriction training and the cyriax technique on pain pressure threshold, function, grip strength, and pinch strength.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This was a randomized clinical trial carried out in the physiotherapy outpatient department of a tertiary care center in Kolhapur City, India.

Participants

Thirty subjects with Lateral epicondylitis were randomly allocated to two groups Blood flow restriction therapy with eccentric exercises and Cyriax therapy with eccentric exercises with 15 subjects in each group. The trial lasted 12 months (18th May 2025 – 30th April 2026). The sample size was computed using the formula, with the alpha value set at 1.96 at a 5% significance level, the beta value set at 1.2816 (90% power), the standard deviation set at 5, and the effect size set at 6 based on prior research. The groups were assigned via lottery, with participants picking chits with the group names inscribed on them. Statistician was blinded to the purpose of the study.[10]

Before the study began, all subjects provided written informed consent. The identity and secrecy of participants were guaranteed, and their rights were respected throughout the trial. CONSORT - 2010 Statement: expansion to pilot studies and feasibility trials guidelines, as well as to preserve the quality of intervention reporting: The TiDier (Template for Intervention Description and Replication) checklist was used. (Fig.1) Individuals aged 19 to 45 who have lateral epicondylitis who had symptoms for more than two weeks, tested positive for Cozen's or Mill's tests,

and had a score of more than three on the Visual Analogue scale were included in the research. Participants were excluded if they had a history of injury around the affected shoulder, elbow, or wrist in the previous 6 months, had primary or secondary metastasis in the upper limb, were pregnant, anaemic, had a history of heart surgery, pulmonary embolism, thrombosis, had upper limb varicose veins, or were on medication for hypertension. No individuals were lost to follow-up after completing the research intervention. [11]

Fig. 1 Consort Flow Diagram

Intervention

Blood Flow Restriction Therapy Group

A skilled physiotherapist performed the intervention. The participants were asked to be seated at a considerable height with forearm and arm exposed. A medium size cuff was used (10 to 12 cm) and it was placed on the arm above the elbow joint. A manual sphygmomanometer was used to measure diastolic (DBP) and systolic (SBP) blood pressure, and an arm circumference was measured by measuring tape. The formula was used to calculate the upper body arterial occlusion and i.e., $0.667(\text{SBP}) + 0.399(\text{DBP}) + 1.461(\text{Arm Circumference}) + 17.236$. The pressure

was calculated as the Percentage of Limb Occlusion Pressure i.e., 50%, and eccentric exercises were given with Blood Flow Restriction Therapy. Three sets of each exercise were given during BFR therapy, with rest intervals between sets of 30 to 60 seconds. Repetition and exercise progression were determined based on the patient's tolerance level. BFR therapy was carried out three times per week for three weeks. [11] (Table 1) (Fig. 2a-2i)

Blood Flow Restriction Therapy With Eccentric Exercises

Cyriax Group

Deep Transverse Friction

Position of the patient- The patient was seated with his or her elbow bent to the right angle and complete supination. The physiotherapist placed one hand on the patient's wrist and supinated the forearm. The pad of the therapist's index, middle, or thumb was put directly over the affected spot, and the remaining fingers were employed to offer further stabilization of the therapist's hand; no lubrication was utilized, and the patient's skin was free to travel over the therapist's fingers. Starting with gentle pressure, the therapist massages the skin over the lesion site back and forth in a manner perpendicular to the natural orientation of the implicated part's fibers. This lasted 2 minutes, paused for 1–2 minutes, and then repeated for 2

minutes, building up to 12-15 minutes before the manipulation.[12] (Fig. 3a)

Mills Manipulation

The patient was seated upright with the affected arm abducted by ninety degrees and with sufficient internal rotation such that the olecranon was facing upward. The therapist placed one hand on the patient's olecranon and used the other hand to hold the patient's wrist in total flexion and pronation. At the end of the elbow extension range of motion, the therapist administered a high velocity, low amplitude push while maintaining the wrist flexed and pronated. [12] (Fig. 3b-3c) Cyriax therapy was given followed by eccentric exercises three times a week for three weeks.

Cyriax Technique

Common Intervention

Eccentric Exercises

Table 1 - Eccentric exercises protocol with progression [13]

Exercise	Repetitions			No. of seconds hold			Progression of load		
	1 ST Week	2 ND Week	3 RD Week	1 ST Week	2 ND Week	3 RD Week	Week k 1	Week k 2	Week 3
The Tyler Twist	5	10	15	3	5	10	Red color flexible rubber Bar		
Eccentric pronation	5	10	15	3	5	10	Yellow thera band	Green thera band	Red thera band
Scaption	5	10	15	3	5	10	Yellow thera band	Green thera band	Red thera band
Eccentric Wrist extension & flexion	5	10	15	5	10	15	½kg dumb bell	1kg dumb bell	2kg dumb bell
Wrist pronation & supination	5	10	15	5	10	15	½kg dumb bell	1kg dumb bell	2kg dumb bell

Ultrasound [14]

Ultrasound therapy was given as conventional therapy to all the participants which was given with a continuous mode for 5 minutes per day, three times per week for three weeks at a frequency of 1MHz and an intensity of 1.5 W/cm² on the lateral epicondyle of the affected arm.

Cryotherapy [14]

Cryotherapy was given after the session for 10 minutes in the form of crushed ice on the lateral epicondyle of the affected arm to reduce the pain and inflammation in that area.

Outcome Measures

The outcomes were assessed at two timelines; at baseline and after completion of the intervention i.e., after 3 weeks.

Objective Outcome:

Grip strength [15]

Jamar grip meter [Sammons Preston Rolyan, UK, Model no. 0205010] was used to measure the grip strength. The patient was in a sitting position with his or her shoulders relaxed, and elbow bent to 90 degrees with forearm straight and the grip meter was given to the patient, to avoid instilling aggression in the participants during testing, the dial was turned to face the tester rather than the participants. Each patient received one practice trial to become acquainted with the instrument. Patients were then instructed to grip the handle as tightly as possible for three seconds while avoiding undue pain. All trials were timed for three seconds using the stopwatch. If the test produced any discomfort, the patient was advised to stop and no more testing was performed. This test was done three times and the average was considered for analysis. The Interclass correlation coefficient for the Jamar grip meter is 0.98.

Pinch strength [16]

Jamar pinch meter [Sammons Preston Rolyan, UK, Model no. 0205010] was used to measure pinch strength. The patient was in a sitting position with his or her shoulders relaxed, elbow bent to 90 degrees, forearm straight, wrist straight with no deviation, and fingers relaxed. To improve grip strength, the thumb pad was positioned midway down the radial side of the first finger at a modest IP flexion angle (15-20%). All trials were timed for three seconds using the stopwatch. If the test produced any discomfort, the patient was advised to stop and no more testing was performed. This test was done three times and the average was considered for analysis. The Interclass correlation coefficient for pinch strength is 0.95

Subjective Outcome:

Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation Questionnaire (PRTEEQ) [17]

The Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation questionnaire was designed exclusively for use with Lateral Epicondylitis. It is a 15-item questionnaire with five items dealing with pain and ten with

functional impairments. For each item, the responder rates the average pain or difficulty they have encountered during the past week while performing several usually uncomfortable tasks in the tennis elbow using a 0- 10 number scale. The scoring method guarantees that pain and function are equally weighted in the overall result. Higher values indicate more severity, with a maximum score of 100. Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation Questionnaire has an interclass correlation value of 0.99.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS 23 software. To confirm that the data distribution was normal, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was used. To investigate the connection between categorical variables, the Fischer t-test was used. For all outcome measures, the independent t-test was employed to compare the mean/distribution between the two groups. To compare the mean/distributions within groups for all variables, a dependent t-test was performed. The significance threshold was set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2: Analysis of Group A and Group B with a mean age & BMI

Variables	Group A		Group B		t-value	p-value
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.		
Age (yrs)	32.40	8.30	30.13	9.56	0.6932	0.4939
Ht (m)	1.67	0.10	1.70	0.09	-0.8837	0.3844
Wt (kg)	67.73	11.18	68.33	13.56	-0.1322	0.8958
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.33	2.66	23.55	3.49	0.6894	0.4962

Group A: BFR Group, Group B: Cyriax group

Table 3a: Within-group analysis of Pre and Post Scores for group A with dependent t-test

Variable	Pre	Post	% of change	Effect size	t-value	p-value
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD				
Grip strength	12.37 \pm 3.99	15.85 \pm 4.46	-28.14	0.8900	-10.668	0.0001*
Pinch strength	4.03 \pm 0.62	5.51 \pm 0.83	-36.69	0.9370	-14.381	0.0001*
PRTEEQ	67.93 \pm 8.51	29.20 \pm 3.91	57.02	0.9730	22.59	0.0001*

Table 3b: Within-group analysis of pre-and post-scores for group B using dependent t-test

Variable	Pre	Post	% of change	Effect size	t-value	p-value
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD				
Grip strength	11.75 \pm 4.58	15.17 \pm 4.73	-29.17	0.96	-19.992	0.0001*
Pinch strength	3.69 \pm 0.90	5.45 \pm 0.91	-37.47	0.9919	-12.614	0.0001*
PRTEEQ	65.20 \pm 8.70	27.00 \pm 4.87	58.59	0.9730	22.5919	0.0001*

dependent t-test *p<0.05

Table 4: Between-group analysis of both groups using an independent t-test

Variable	Time frame	Group	Mean \pm SD	t-value	p-value
Grip strength	Pre	Grp-A	12.37 \pm 3.99	0.3953	0.6956
		Grp-B	11.75 \pm 4.58		
	Post	Grp-A	15.85 \pm 4.46	0.4009	0.6915
		Grp-B	15.17 \pm 4.73		
	Diff	Grp-A	3.48 \pm 1.26	0.1447	0.8860
		Grp-B	3.43 \pm 0.66		
Pinch strength	Pre	Grp-A	4.03 \pm 0.62	1.2056	0.2381
		Grp-B	3.69 \pm 0.90		
	Post	Grp-A	5.51 \pm 0.83	0.2091	0.8359
		Grp-B	5.45 \pm 0.91		
	Diff	Grp-A	1.48 \pm 0.40	-1.5804	0.1252
		Grp-B	1.75 \pm 0.54		
PRTEEQ	Pre	Grp-A	67.93 \pm 8.51	0.8695	0.3920
		Grp-B	65.20 \pm 8.70		
	Post	Grp-A	29.20 \pm 3.91	1.3639	0.1835
		Grp-B	27.00 \pm 4.87		
	Diff	Grp-A	38.73 \pm 8.67	0.1901	0.8506
		Grp-B	38.20 \pm 6.55		

#Independent t-test *p<0.05. Group A: Blood flow restriction, Group B: Cyriax

RESULTS

Thirty participants were randomly assigned into two groups having 15 participants in each group. The mean age of individuals was 32.40 \pm 8.30 in the Blood flow restriction group and 30.13 \pm 9.56 in the Cyriax

group. The mean BMI of individuals was 24.33 \pm 2.66 in the Blood flow restriction group and 23.55 \pm 3.49 in the Cyriax group. The demographic data of the participants are specified in Table 2. Dependent t-test was used to compare the mean changes within both groups. The Blood flow restriction group showed significant percentage improvement for all the outcomes i.e., Grip strength with -28.14% (p =

0.0001*), Pinch strength with -36.69% ($p = 0.0001^*$) and Patient rated tennis elbow evaluation questionnaire with 57.02 % ($p = 0.0001^*$) (Table 2a) However, in the Cyriax group, the percentage change was significant for Grip strength at -29.17% ($p = 0.0001^*$), Pinch strength at -37.47 % ($p = 0.0001^*$) and Patient rated tennis elbow evaluation questionnaire at 58.59 % ($p = 0.0001^*$) (Table 2b) Changes in variables between the group were tested by an independent t-test that suggested both groups to be equally effective for Grip strength ($p = 0.8860$), pinch strength ($p = 0.1252$), and Patient rated tennis elbow evaluation questionnaire with ($p = 0.8506$).

DISCUSSION

The current study accepted the null hypothesis, as there was no change in Pain pressure threshold, function, grip, and pinch strength between the Blood flow restriction group and the Cyriax group. There was an increase in grip & pinch strength when eccentric exercises were added. The Blood flow restriction training approach may have resulted in these findings because it used low-intensity loading that did not cause discomfort in the individuals during muscular contraction, which subjects tend to feel more comfortable during exercise and increase muscle mass. Secondly, in Blood flow restriction there is muscle tension and metabolic stress which takes place and they are responsible for muscle hypertrophy. When the muscle is mechanically stressed, the concentration of anabolic hormone levels rises. The activation of myogenic stem cells and the increased hormone levels cause protein metabolism and, as a result, muscular growth. When myogenic stem cells are triggered in response to muscular injury or tendinitis, they repair damaged muscle fibers while simultaneously promoting fiber development in the wounded location. Third, eccentric workouts greatly boost insulin-like growth hormone, which is responsible for increased collagen production and muscle repair. In addition, hypoxia develops as a result of blood vessel compression during exercise. This results in a hypoxic environment because the muscle receives less oxygen. The hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF-1) is activated as a result of the hypoxia, increasing anaerobic lactic metabolism and lactate generation. Furthermore, as blood pools, a buildup of metabolites induces cell swelling. The swelling within

the cells triggers an anabolic response, resulting in muscular growth. As a result of muscular hypertrophy, the cross-sectional area of the muscle fibers increases, and the muscle generates more strength. These results are in agreement with a previous study conducted by Gede Parta Kinandana which stated that there was an increase in hand and pinch strength improvement in function by using Blood flow restriction therapy with low-load exercises. [11,18-19] In response to the cyriax, pain relief was noted with the administration of Deep transverse friction and mill manipulation. First, the patient may feel a numbing effect throughout the treatment, resulting in less pain. This is due to a rise in the breakdown of pain-inducing metabolites such as Lewis' compounds. Second, diffused noxious inhibitory controls, a pain suppression mechanism that generates endogenous opiates, can be employed to lessen pain. These are inhibitory neurotransmitters that lessen the strength of pain signals sent by higher centers. Third, immediately after Deep transverse friction, the mill's manipulation is used to stretch the terrified tissue by rupturing adhesions inside the Teno-osseous junction, making the area mobile and pain-free. This was consistent with Prabhakar AJ's study, which found that cyriax physiotherapy combined with eccentric movements helps reduce discomfort in tennis elbow patients. [12] There was an increase in the grip and pinch strength when added to the eccentric exercises. Eccentric exercise causes tendon strengthening by activating mechanoreceptors in tenocytes to create collagen, which is the fundamental biological process that affects tendon injury healing. Strengthening may enhance collagen alignment of the tendon and induce cross-linkage development, improving tensile strength and hence grip and pinch strength. This was in accordance with the study done by Stasinopoulos et al where he concluded that supervised eccentric exercises along with cyriax physiotherapy produced the largest effect in reducing pain, improving functions and grip strength.[20] Improvement in quality of life was observed in the cyriax group. The study done by R Vishwas stated that there was improved quality of life in individuals who received cyriax therapy sessions with low-load training. This could be due to the deep transverse friction and mills manipulation with eccentric exercises which increase muscular strength and reduce pain hence improving quality of life. [21]

Similar results were seen in the BFR group which was in accordance with the study done by Stefanos Karanasios which stated that there was improved quality of life in individuals who received Blood flow restriction therapy sessions with low-load training. This could be due to the occlusion of blood flow with eccentric exercises which increases muscular strength and reduces pain hence the quality of life was improved. [18] Both treatments showed to be effective in terms of grip strength, pinch strength, and quality of life which could be due to conventional physiotherapy (Ultrasound therapy and cryotherapy) which was consistent with a prior study that showed ultrasound causes vibration in the tissue, producing small bubbles to convey vibrations that directly excite cell membranes. This tactile stimulation appears to boost the inflammatory response's cell-repair effects, reducing discomfort. Cryotherapy restricts blood flow to a specific area, which can significantly reduce inflammation and swelling that causes pain, especially around a joint or tendon. It can temporarily suppress nerve activity, which assists in pain alleviation. [22]

Strengths, Limitations & Future Scope

Blood flow restriction therapy is a novel and advanced therapy which was compared to a gold standard technique i.e., the cyriax technique, and was proven to be equally effective for lateral epicondylitis. As this study concluded that both the treatments showed similar results, either of both can be used according to the therapist and patient's convenience. The study had some limitations, including the lack of a control group, which prevented extensive comparisons of the two regimens. There was no follow-up to evaluate the long-term impact of the therapies. This intervention was administered in addition to conventional therapy, such as ultrasound therapy and cryotherapy, which may have obscured the effects of blood flow restriction therapy and cyriax therapy. This study can be conducted in individuals suffering from chronic Lateral epicondylitis and also in other chronic conditions to assess the effects. Blood flow restriction and Cyriax can be studied in different tendinopathies such as rotator cuff tendinopathy and frozen shoulder. A follow-up study can be carried out to evaluate the long-term effects of BFR and Cyriax.

CONCLUSION

The present study concluded that blood flow restriction therapy and Cyriax technique when given in combination with eccentric exercises and conventional treatment are equally effective in improving function, grip strength, and pinch strength in lateral epicondylitis. Both interventions are effective in managing the condition and should be incorporated by the clinicians, and physical therapists as per their skill and expertise.

Clinical relevance

This study will provide valuable clinical evidence comparing the effectiveness of Blood Flow Restriction Therapy and Cyriax Technique as adjuncts to eccentric exercise in the management of lateral epicondylitis. The findings may help physiotherapists choose the most effective, time-efficient, and evidence-based approach to improve grip strength, and restore functional ability in patients with tennis elbow.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Hamilton PG. The prevalence of humeral epicondylitis: a survey in general practice. *The Journal of the Royal College of General Practitioners*. 1986 Oct 1;36(291):464-5.
2. Dimberg L. The prevalence and causation of tennis elbow (lateral humeral epicondylitis) in a population of workers in the engineering industry. *Ergonomics*. 1987 Mar 1;30(3):573-9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140138708969746>
3. Walz DM, Newman JS, Konin GP, Ross G. Epicondylitis: pathogenesis, imaging, and treatment. *Radiographics*. 2010 Jan;30(1):167-84. <https://doi.org/10.1148/rg.301095078>
4. Johnson GW, Cadwallader K, Scheffel SB, Epperly TD. Treatment of lateral epicondylitis.

- Am Fam Physician. 2007 Sep 15;76(6):843-8. PMID: 17910298.
5. Balasubramanian R, Manikumar M, Shivakumar HB. Effect Of Ischemic Compression Therapy with Eccentric Exercises on Selected Outcome Variables in Tennis Elbow Patients-A Pilot Study. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*. 2022 Mar 23;6(3):1542- 6.
 6. Scott BR, Loenneke JP, Slattery KM, Dascombe BJ. Exercise with blood flow restriction: an updated evidence-based approach for enhanced muscular development. *Sports medicine*. 2015;45(3):313-25.
 7. Wilson JM, Lowery RP, Joy JM, Loenneke JP, Naimo MA. Practical blood flow restriction training increases acute hypertrophy determinants without increasing muscle damage indices. *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*. 2013;27(11):3068-75
10.1519/JSC.0b013e31828a1ffa
 8. Cyriax HJ, Cyriax JP. *Cyriax's illustrated manual of orthopedic medicine*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann, 1983.
 9. Stasinopoulos D, Johnson MI. Cyriax physiotherapy for tennis elbow/lateral epicondylitis. *British Journal of sports medicine*. 2004 Dec 1;38(6):675-7.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bjism.2004.013573>
 10. Shimizu R, Hotta K, Yamamoto S, Matsumoto T, Kamiya K, Kato M, Hamazaki N, Kamekawa D, Akiyama A, Kamada Y, Tanaka S. Low-intensity resistance training with blood flow restriction improves vascular endothelial function and peripheral blood circulation in healthy elderly people. *European Journal of applied physiology*. 2016 Apr;116:749-57.
 11. Kinandana GP, Dewi AA, Winaya IM, Antari NK, Wibawa A, Adhitya IP. The Efficacy of Blood Flow Restriction Training for Grip Strength and Disability in Lateral Epicondylitis. *Bali Medical Journal*. 2023 Jan 25;12(1):410-5.
<https://doi.org/10.15562/bmj.v12i1.3973>
 12. Prabhakar AJ, Kage V, Anap D. Effectiveness of Cyriax physiotherapy in subjects with tennis elbow. *J Nov Physiother*. 2013;3(3):156.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2165-7025.1000156>
 13. Tyler TF, Thomas GC, Nicholas SJ, McHugh MP. Addition of isolated wrist extensor eccentric exercise to standard treatment for chronic lateral epicondylitis: a prospective randomized trial. *Journal of Shoulder and Elbow surgery*. 2010 Sep 1;19(6):917-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jse.2010.04.041>
 14. Öken Ö, Kahraman Y, Ayhan F, Canpolat S, Yorgancioglu ZR, Öken ÖF. The short-term efficacy of laser, brace, and ultrasound treatment in lateral epicondylitis: a prospective, randomized, controlled trial. *Journal of Hand Therapy*. 2008 Jan 1;21(1):63-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1197/j.jht.2007.09.003>
 15. Amro A, Diener I, Isra' M H, Shalabi AI, Dua' I I. The effects of Mulligan mobilisation with movement and taping techniques on pain, grip strength, and function in patients with lateral epicondylitis. *Hong Kong Physiotherapy Journal*. 2010 Jan 1;28(1):19-23.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hkpj.2010.11.004>
 16. MacDermid JC, Evenhuis W, Louzon M. Inter-instrument reliability of pinch strength scores. *Journal of hand therapy*. 2001 Jan 1;14(1):36-42
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0894-1130\(01\)80023-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0894-1130(01)80023-5)
 17. Rompe JD, Overend TJ, MacDermid JC. Validation of the patient-rated tennis elbow evaluation questionnaire. *Journal of Hand Therapy*. 2007 Jan 1;20(1):3-11
<https://doi.org/10.1197/j.jht.2006.10.003>
 18. Wideman L, Weltman JY, Hartman ML, Veldhuis JD, Weltman A. Growth hormone release during acute and chronic aerobic and resistance exercise. *Sports medicine*. 2002 Dec 1;32(15):987-1004.
 19. Wilson JM, Lowery RP, Joy JM, Loenneke JP, Naimo MA. Practical blood flow restriction training increases acute determinants of hypertrophy without increasing indices of muscle damage. *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*. 2013 Nov 1;27(11):3068-75.
10.1519/JSC.0b013e31828a1ffa
 20. Stasinopoulos D, Stasinopoulou K, Johnson MI. An exercise programme for the management of lateral elbow tendinopathy. *British journal of sports medicine*. 2005 Dec 1;39(12):944-7.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bjism.2005.019836>
 21. Viswas R, Ramachandran R, Korde Anantkumar P. Comparison of effectiveness of supervised exercise program and Cyriax physiotherapy in patients with tennis elbow (lateral epicondylitis): a randomized clinical trial. *The scientific world*

journal. 2012 May;2012.
<https://doi.org/10.1100/2012/939645>

22. Binder A, Hodge G, Greenwood AM, Hazleman BL, Thomas DP. Is therapeutic ultrasound effective in treating soft tissue lesions?. Br Med J (Clin Res Ed). 1985 Feb 16;290(6467):512
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.290.6467.512>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20808752>

